

DEUTSCHES HERZZENTRUM
DER CHARITÉ

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AI-based prediction of transvalvular pressure gradients in aortic stenosis

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1. Introduction

1.1 Aortic Valve Disease

Aortic Valve Disease - Overview

Aortic Valve Disease - Echocardiography

$$\text{TPG} = 4 \cdot v^2$$

Aortic Valve Disease - Catheterization

$$TPG = P_1 - P_2$$

Aortic Valve Disease – TPG Quantification

■ Echocardiography

Advantages:

- Cost effective
- Non-invasive

Shortcomings:

- Inaccurate Assumptions
- Operator Bias

■ Catherization

Advantages:

- Accurate
- Reliable

Shortcomings:

- Expensive
- Invasive

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1. Introduction

1.2 Image Based Modelling

Image Based Modelling

Aortic Valve Disease – TPG Quantification

▪ Echocardiography

Advantages:

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▪ IBM

Advantages:

- Accurate
- Non-invasive

Shortcomings:

- Computational costs

Image Based Modelling

Image Based Modelling

Image Based Modelling

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2. Methods

Artificial Neural Network – Development

Artificial Neural Network – Centerline-based Representation

Artificial Neural Network – Architecture

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3. Results

ANN vs. CFD – Examples

ANN vs. CFD – Average Performance on 23 Test Cases

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (P_{iANN} - P_{iCFD})^2}{N}}$$

$$NRMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{P_{iANN} - P_{iCFD}}{P_{1CFD} - \inf\{P_{1CFD}, \dots, P_{NCFD}\}} \right)^2}{N}}$$

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4. Conclusion

ANN-based hemodynamic Modelling

- Good Agreement between CFD and ANN
- Wide Range of TPG covered
- Predictive Capabilities (e.g. Stress Testing)
- Local Inaccuracies remain
- Steady State only at this Point
- Underlying CFD unvalidated

→ ANN is feasible for hemodynamic Computations

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4. Outlook

Potential Improvement

ML Method:

- More Input Parameters
- Higher spatial Resolution
- More Training Data
- Different Architecture?

CFD Method:

- Unsteady Simulations
- Compare with clinical TPG Data
- Fluid Structure Interaction

Thank you for your Attention!

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